

Enabling an Open Innovation Model for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co-Creation with FabLabs, Safety Experts and Customer Communities

WP3- ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development
Deliverable D3.2: "ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v1"

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

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ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v1

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market Trend Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D3.2 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v1” is used to document the initial designs regarding the ToyLabs core platform and the different components to be implemented and integrated in the platform as tasks under WP4.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the designs, workflow diagrams and other work that has been performed under the WP3 tasks in the previous period. All these outputs, can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

D3.2 will be updated throughout the project and those amendments will result to deliverables D3.3, D3.4 and finally D3.5. Each one of those new versions, will provide new insights and design document to the software development tasks of WP4, in order to gradually describe the features and functions necessary to reach a stable version of the ToyLabs MVP.

Furthermore, the prioritized backlog that is presented in D3.2 might be also altered in those revised versions, by adding new user stories or by removing some obsolete ones, resulting into specific changes to the MVP, agreed by all consortium partners.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D3.2 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v1” is used to document the initial designs regarding the ToyLabs core platform and the different components to be implemented and integrated in the platform as tasks under WP4.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the designs, workflow diagrams and other work that has been performed under the WP3 tasks in the previous period. All these outputs, can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

D3.2 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the ToyLabs MVP, and acts as a continuation of the work started in D3.1, towards defining which elements of the backlog are going to be released with a priority
- Section 3 includes design documents of the different components
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable, stating the next imminent steps to be executed and documented under the upcoming deliverable D3.3

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

As identified in the DoA, D3.2 is tightly linked to all other WP3 deliverables, as well as to all WP4 Deliverables.

Regarding WP3, D3.2 will be revised continuously throughout the project and will be the basis for deliverables D3.3, D3.4 and D3.5, which all concern the updated designs and technical diagrams that will be created with a view on the upcoming releases of the ToyLabs agile development process.

With regards to WP4, D3.2 provides the initial list of design documents, as well as of the feature that will act as input to the development tasks. Furthermore, D3.2 acts as a reference document regarding the evaluation of the output of the software development tasks, which will be constantly checked to amend as necessary the backlog and its prioritised list.

2 THE TOYLABS MVP

2.1 User Stories Voting – Backlog Prioritisation

The user stories of the platform have been already defined in the previous deliverable (D3.1). In order to be able to construct the MVP, a simple prioritisation model was used which calculated the value of a user story, against the necessary costs. To decide what valuable means, first the primary goal of the product is defined, followed by the definition of a main process which the user follows in order to reach that goal.

The final scoring of the user stories has been extracted by putting into the equation the preferences/votes of all partners, as well as applying a corrective coefficient, in order to group together user stories that are deemed as essential for the smooth operation of the platform.

The complete ordered list of the user stories that constitute the backlog can be found in Annex A.

2.2 The ToyLabs MVP

The Minimum Viable Product (MVP) is all about validating the more crucial hypotheses of a product, which if they fail the whole idea is not functional any more.

By collecting User Stories for each component that have an overall score from **20 to 25**, the critical implementation of the overall platform could be defined. Grouping together the ones that are related, different component sprints are formed. Based on the described prioritization approach, the following user stories were selected as the most valuable and critical ones.

In more detail, the MVP to be rolled out as the functional version of the ToyLabs platform would cater for the following user actions:

- Visitors should be able to:
 - Browse the public catalogue of the product
 - Register to become Ordinary Users
- Ordinary Users should be able to:
 - Log In
 - Update their Profile
 - Choose a Role
 - Comment on Products
 - Trigger AR visualisations
 - Communicate with other Users via Message
- Manufacturers should be able to:

- Create an entry for a new Product
- Create Designs linked to the Product
- Search for Partner
- Invite a partner to a design
- Create Prototypes linked to the Product
- Invite a partner to a Prototype
- Upload AR models
- Obtain feedback from AR models
- FabLabs should be able to:
 - Respond on Manufacturers Invitations
 - Access Product Designs
 - Comment on Product Designs
 - Access Product Prototypes
 - Comment on Product Prototypes
- Experts
 - Respond on Manufacturers Invitations
 - Access Product Designs
 - Comment on Product Designs
 - Access Product Prototypes
 - Comment on Product Prototypes
 - Comment AR models
- Organisation Owners should be able to:
 - Create an Organisation
 - Add Members to an Organisation
- Product Owners should be able to:
 - Initiate the Production of a Product
 - Monitor the Production of a Product

On the basis of the ToyLabs MVP, the consortium will focus on filling in the platform with products (including designs and prototypes) that the partners have already implemented and continue to support, in order to get early feedback from customers and see how they are engaged with the content that describes a product.

At the same time User stories that score between 15 and 19 are considered as valuable but not essential for the first stable release. These stories may be added in later iterations and lead to a more refined implementation of the ToyLabs platform

The proposed MVP with its selected features will be continuously validated and adapted to the requirements of customers or development teams but also towards ethical and technical constraints.

3 TOYLABS COMPONENTS DESCRIPTIONS

3.1 ToyLabs Core Platform

3.1.1 Introduction

This is the main infrastructure that powers the ToyLabs platform and is the host environment for all other sub-components that need to be integrated.

In more detail, the TCP is responsible for handling the following main operations requested from the overall project platform:

- Platform Browsing
- Registration/Log In
- Profile Editing
- Organisation Selection
- ToyLabs Products Browsing
- Communication Actions
- Feedback Provision
- Product Initiation
- Prototype Request
- Product Handling
- Design Handling
- Prototype Handling
- AR model handling
- Feedback to Design
- Feedback to Prototype
- Feedback to AR model
- Product Information Filling
- Manufacturing Initiation
- Product Monitoring
- Organisation Information Filling
- Organisation Management
- Participating in an Organisation

3.1.2 Component's High-Level Architecture

The TCP relies on a three-tier architecture, that is based on technologies such as MariaDB¹ for the backend system, PHP² for the middle application layer and PHP and JavaScript³ libraries for the frontend.

The proposed architecture has been selected in order to guarantee the smooth operation of the overall infrastructure, the safeguarding of the data stored in the system, as well as the ability of the TCP to integrate and get interconnected with other third-party tools, as well as the option to change the UI at different times.

A high-level description of the TCP architecture is provided in the next figure.

Figure 1: TCP High Level Architecture

¹ <https://mariadb.org>

² <https://www.w3schools.com/pHp/default.asp>

³ <https://www.javascript.com>

3.1.3 Component’s Flow Diagrams

The user is able to browse all the “public” pages of the ToyLabs platform, as no authorization is required to see the information that is publically published. Upon landing to the user login/registration page, he is able to either log in using his credentials (in case he has been already registered in ToyLabs), or to initiate the registration process. This process asks the user for specific information, and once he is accepted as a registered user he may choose whether to join an existing organization or create a new one. As a next step, the user is able to browse the platform’s private spaces, and also to edit his profile.

Figure 2: User Onboarding Workflow

The creation of a product on the ToyLabs platform is initiated by a user by specifying some basic information about the product. Afterwards the user is able to create different design or prototype version, and in each one add collaborators and work with them in order to improve the product. It needs to be noted, that during the whole process, specific parts (like “Add Collaborator”) are supported by other components such as the PMN component.

Figure 3: Product Management Workflow

3.1.4 Early Mockups

Figure 4: ToyLabs Products Showcase

Figure 5: Registration/Login Page

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "ToyLabs - Register" with the URL "http://toylabs.eu/register". The page features the ToyLabs logo at the top center. Below the logo, there is a registration form with the following fields: "Name", "Email", "Password", and "Confirm". A checkbox labeled "I agree to Terms and Conditions" is checked. At the bottom of the form, there is a link "Already have an account? Go to the [Login](#) page" and an orange "Register" button with a right-pointing arrow.

Figure 6: User Registration Form

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "ToyLabs - Edit Profile" with the URL "http://toylabs.eu/profile/edit". The page has a navigation bar with "ToyLabs", "Home", "Products", and "About" links, and a user profile icon for "John Doe". The main content area is titled "Edit Profile" and contains the following fields: "Name" (pre-filled with "John Doe"), "Address", "Country" (a dropdown menu), "Telephone", "Facebook", "Twitter", and "Linkedin". Below these fields, there is a section for "Professional Toy Manufacturer" with an "Organization:" label and the text "You haven't joined any organization yet." There are "Join" and "Create" buttons. At the bottom of the form, there are "Cancel" and "Update" buttons.

Figure 7: User Profile Page

Figure 8: Products' Monitoring Dashboard

Figure 9: Product Detail page, including designs, prototypes and comments

3.2 Market and Trend Analysis Component

3.2.1 Introduction

This component is intended to give the user an easy to use tool that will provide him with the appropriate information - through various, intuitive charts- to help him on the one hand identify market trends for his domain of interest and on the other hand gain a deeper understanding of customers' satisfaction and dissatisfaction on specific topics (either products/toys or brands) and as a result on their brand perception, campaign efficiency and competitors' position in the market.

Through this component, the toy manufacturer, or any intended user, will be able to acquire important social feedback, analyse it through easy-to-grasp visual analytics and draw useful conclusions on emerging market trends for the toy industry, that may serve as recommendations and initial, raw ideas about future toy designs.

3.2.2 Component's High-level Architecture

The Market and Trend Analysis component consists of three main, distinct parts; the User Interface, the Communication Layer and the Natural Language Processing and Analytics engine. Figure 10 depicts the component's high level architecture, namely these three layers along with their internal structure.

The User Interface is responsible for providing the user with insights into the collected data, while guiding him to apply filters, make intuitive queries and browse the results through advanced visualisations. The component's User Interface in question will be connected with the platform's User Interface. The basic technologies to be used to this layer are Javascript, "Django" framework and libraries "D3" and "AMCHARTS".

The Communication layer manages or directs the flow of data between the two other layers, namely the component's User Interface and the Analytics engine. The "Flask" framework will be used for this purpose.

Finally, the Natural language processing and analytics engine is responsible for the data retrieval, data processing and the implementation of all required computations to perform emotion analysis and identify trending topics. As a result, this layer is used to extract data from source and process them in a way that can feed the web interface. The basic technologies that are used are the "Elasticsearch" engine, the "Couchbase" database, the "NLTK" framework and the "Scikit learn" library.

Figure 10: Architecture of Market and Trend Analysis Component

3.2.3 Component's Flow Diagrams

The first workflow presented in Figure 11 has to do with the configuration of each newly created project. The user must initialize a harvester in order to start a trend or a social feedback analysis and this is achieved via a group of settings that the user must provide to platform. These settings has to do with the data sources to be used for the analysis, the keywords, hashtags or phrases considered as representative of the analysis that will follow and which must be included in the harvesting data, data's allowable publication times and data's language. The component enables also the user to create market sets (i.e. group of products, brands, product types) in order to use these as input to social feedback analysis and possibly to harvester. When data harvesting is completed, the component sends a notification e-mail to the user to start his analysis.

Figure 11: Project Configuration Workflow

According to the flow diagram presented in Figure 12, the user may choose all or part of harvesting data for a simple or a comparative trend analysis or load past saved search settings. In either case, he may afterwards provide to the platform additional settings regarding the time period, the sources and the languages of the data for the analysis. After that, he can initiate a trend analysis and apply specific filters to charts in order to acquire the needed information. The user can also save these preferences for future use.

Figure 12: Trend Analysis Workflow

Finally, Figure 13 represents the flow diagram for the user that wants to implement social feedback analysis. For the social feedback analysis, the user is firstly asked by the platform to choose a market set to be used for the analysis, either for a “simple” analysis for the user’s brand and products or a comparative one, taking into account also the competitors’ presence. If a market set has not been specified before, during the project configuration, the user is directed back there to determine at least one. Then the user can start social feedback analysis and apply, as was the case in trend analysis, specific filters to charts in order to take the information he needs and to save these preferences for future use.

Figure 13: Social Feedback Workflow

3.2.4 Early Mockups

Figure 14: ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Landing page

ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Initialisation

http://toylabs.eu/markettrends/harvester

Initialize Project

Provide a name for your project

Included Keywords or hashtags

[+ Advanced Settings](#)

Market Set

My Brands

Brand Name

...

Only for Social Feedback Analysis

My Products

Product Name

...

Only for Social Feedback Analysis

Sources

Source type: Source 1 Source 2 Source 3 Source 4

Source:

Language:

Time: From To

Influencers

Define Influencers' s Accounts

Figure 15: Project's Initialisation page

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Initialisation" with the URL "http://toylabs.eu/marketrends/harvester". The main heading is "Initialise Project".

Project Name
[Text input field]

Included Keywords or hashtags
[Text input field: key1 OR key2 OR key3]
- [Advanced Settings](#)

[Text input field: key1 AND key2 AND key3] Concept1
[+]

Market Set
My Brands

Brand Name
Please fill your brand name (one or more)
[Text input field]

[Text input field: Competitor 1]
[Text input field: Competitor 2]
...
[Text input field: Competitor n]
[+]

Only for Social Feedback Analysis

My Products

Product Name
Please fill your product name (one or more)
[Text input field]

[Text input field: Competitive product 1]
[Text input field: Competitive product 2]
...
[Text input field: Competitive product n]
[+]

Only for Social Feedback Analysis

Sources

Source type: Source 1
 Source 2
 Source 3
 Source 4

Source: [Dropdown: Available Sources] [+]

Language: [Dropdown: Available Languages]

Time: From [Date] To [Date]

Influencers

Define Influencers' s Accounts
[Text area]

[Save Changes] [Cancel]

Figure 16: Project's Initialisation page /Advanced Settings enabled

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Initialisation" with the URL "http://toylibs.eu/marketrends/harvester". The main heading is "Initialise Project".

Project Name: A text input field.

Included Keywords or hashtags: A text input field containing "key1 OR key2 OR key3".

- Advanced Settings: A blue-bordered box containing:

- A text input field with "key1 AND key2 AND key3" and a "Rename" button next to it.
- The text "Concept1" with a small icon.
- The word "OR" in the center.
- A text input field with "key1 AND key2 AND key3" and "Concept2" next to it.
- A "+" button at the bottom.

Market Set:

- My Brands:** A "Brand Name" input field with the instruction "Please fill your brand name (one or more)". To its right are input fields for "Competitor 1", "Competitor 2", and "Competitor n". A checkbox "Only for Social Feedback Analysis" is present.
- My Products:** A "Product Name" input field with the instruction "Please fill your product name (one or more)". To its right are input fields for "Competitive product 1", "Competitive product 2", and "Competitive product n". A checkbox "Only for Social Feedback Analysis" is present.

Sources:

- Source type:** Radio buttons for "Source 1", "Source 2", "Source 3", and "Source 4".
- Source:** A dropdown menu showing "Available Sources".
- Language:** A dropdown menu showing "Available Languages".
- Time:** "From" and "To" date pickers.
- A "+" button.

Influencers: A large text area with the instruction "Define Influencers' s Accounts".

At the bottom are "Save Changes" and "Cancel" buttons.

Figure 17: Project's Initialisation page/ Advanced Settings enabled / Adding concepts & renaming

Figure 18: Trend Analysis Set up page

Figure 19: User's Trend Analysis Saved Settings

Figure 20: Trend Analysis Custom Set up page

Figure 21: Trend Analysis Dashboard

Figure 22: Social Feedback Set up page

Figure 23: Social Feedback Analysis Dashboard

3.3 Augmented Reality Feedback Component

3.3.1 Introduction

The Augmented Reality Feedback Component (ARF Component or ARFC) is a tool used by end user that allow responsive and interactive presentation of 3D models with advanced capabilities.

Main goal of this tool is to obtain feedback and related recommendations for improving new product designs.

The ARFC will use 3 different modules: Questionnaire Creation to obtain feedback from user, Augmented Reality System for model presentation (rotation, modifying parameters like color, textures,..) and Voting System used to know specific features on an AR model on mobile devices.

3.3.2 Component's High-level Architecture

The ARF component is an infrastructure that relies also on a three-tier architecture.

Figure 24 shows the backend that consist of an MySQL⁴ database with several tables which is being used to store server path for previously uploaded 3D models, textures or other parameters on one side on other side a table should be defined with standard tracking parameters ready to be used by end user or product owner (jpg, pdf, ...)

The Architecture will be supported by an AR Engine or any development thought AR SDK development (please see D2.1, section 2.4 about AR SDKs available).

On the User side the ARF component will be supported by a survey infrastructure that can help developer and end user to obtain feedback and related recommendations for improving new product designs. This survey infrastructure will be integrated on general survey engine module from platform.

Also on user side, the ARF component will use a Voting System, this infrastructure will be integrated using general voting engine module developed on platform.

⁴ <https://www.mysql.com>

Figure 24: ARF High Level Architecture

3.3.3 Component's Flow Diagrams

As indicated in D2.1, the ARF component is used to allow users (Childhood Experts/End-Users, Childhood Experts/End-Users, FabLabs ,..) to send feedback to developers (Manufacturer, FabLabs, ...) on predefined 3D Models and product definition.

As defined in D2.1, and deeply described, workflow will cover different activities:

- A. Attach an AR model to a prototype
- B. Accompany the AR model with a simple questionnaire for AR user
- C. Upload a screenshot of AR model
- D. Comment on an AR model
- E. Vote for specific features on an AR model on mobile devices (FabLab, experts)
- F. Manipulate controls of the AR model

The following table lists the different stakeholder teams that will use the Augmented Reality Module as well as the specific functionalities intended for each team.

Table 3-1. Companies profile.

Stakeholder	Features
Manufacturer	A, B, C
FabLabs	C, D, E, F
Safety/Environmental Experts	C, D, E, F
Childhood Experts/End-Users	C, D, E, F

Figure 25 below presents the workflow performed by a manufacturer that is willing to showcase an AR model. He is able to check for existing material on the platform, develop new material and after defining the target audience launch the AR model and explore the results of the feedback.

Figure 25: Manufacturer Workflow

On the other side, Figure 26 shows how experts, FabLabs and other individuals or organizations are able to select an AR model (probably on their mobile phone), explore it through its visualization features and then provide feedback to the manufacturer, that could be either in the form of a structured questionnaire, or through a voting system.

Figure 26: Fablabs/Safety Expert/Environmental Expert/ Childhood Experts/ End users Workflow

3.3.4 Early Mockups

Figure 27: Manufacturer Main AR Menu

Figure 28: Fablabs/Safety Expert/Environmental Expert/ Childhood Experts/ End users Main AR Menu

Figure 29: Attach an AR Model / Screenshots

Figure 30: AR model Viewer

Figure 31: AR model Viewer Mobile Version

Figure 32: Edit/Create AR Questionnaire

Figure 33: Adding Questions to AR Questionnaire

Figure 34: AR Questionnaire Result Screen

Figure 35: Managing Features for Voting

Figure 36: Create Feature for Voting

Figure 37: Voting Results Screen

3.4 Partner Matching and Negotiation Component

3.4.1 Introduction

The partner matching component is a tool that is used by users in order to seek collaborators inside the ToyLabs platform and allow them to set up formal partnerships that will lead to collaborative design and development of products.

In more detail, the PMN component is responsible for handling a handful of operations that range from partner searching to matchmaking between different platform users to enable specific collaboration opportunities. Based on the analysis provided in D3.1, the PMN is tasked to support the following main operations:

- Partner Matching
- Contract Negotiation
- FabLab Contract Opportunity
- Expert Contract Opportunity

3.4.2 Component’s High-level Architecture

The PMN component is an infrastructure that relies also on a three-tier architecture.

The backend consists of a MySQL⁵ database which is being used to store data regarding the different partners, as well as other information, such as active or past collaborations. The middle layer is responsible for the application logic and executes the partner search queries as well as the different partner matching algorithms.

A high-level description of the TCP architecture is provided in the next figure.

⁵ <https://www.mysql.com>

Figure 38: PMN High Level Architecture

3.4.3 Component's Flow Diagrams

As indicated in the previous deliverables, the PMN component is used to allow users to seek for collaborators. This is based on the process of triggering a query which returns the possible collaborators that match the user's search criteria, which can be constantly refined until a short list is displayed. Out of the short list, the user may choose his preferred collaborator, send him an NDA accompanied by a collaboration request, and upon acceptance a contract to be signed.

Figure 39: Partner Searching and Selection Workflow

3.4.4 Early Mockups

Figure 40: Partner Type Selection

Figure 41: Partner Matching Search

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 At a glance

D3.2 includes the initial technical design documents which are provided for the development of the core ToyLabs platform, as well as for the different components that have been identified and described in the previous stages of the project. Those are all included in the project’s GitHub account at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs> and formulate the core material upon which WP4 will work to deliver the software platform.

Accompanying those documents, D3.2 includes also the first prioritised list of the backlog that has been constructed in D3.1, and thus is able to propose the first version of the ToyLabs MVP that included the essential features that should make it to the development tasks.

4.2 Next Steps

As discussed in the introduction, D3.2 will be updated throughout the project and those amendments will result to deliverables D3.3, D3.4 and finally D3.5. Each one of those new versions, will provide new insights and design document to the software development tasks of WP4, in order to gradually describe the features and functions necessary to reach a stable version of the ToyLabs MVP. Furthermore, the prioritized backlog that is presented in D3.2 might be also altered in those revised versions, by adding new user stories or by removing some obsolete ones, resulting into specific changes to the MVP, agreed by all consortium partners.

ANNEX A: TOYLABS BACKLOG

User Stories ranked between 25,00 and 20,00

#	EPIC	As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
VI.1	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to find out more about the ToyLabs project from the main platform		I can understand how the project operates
OU.30	Product Initiation		Ordinary User		to be able to initiate a product creation phase		I can become a product owner
PO.1	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to be able to fill in the basic information about a new product		I can provide more details on that product
MA.35	Prototype handling		Manufacturer		to create a new "Prototype"		I can open up the prototyping phase of the process
OU.2	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to choose the role that I will have in ToyLabs (Manufacturer, FabLab, Safety Expert, Childhood Expert, Ordinary User)		I can enjoy the services offered to the role I belong to
FA.6	Feedback to Designs		FabLab		to be able to download all material in a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
MA.11	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to attach to the "Open Request" call an NDA		I can protect my IPRs
FA.1	Fablab Contract Opportunity		FabLab		to get notified about a direct invite I might get from a manufacturer		I can reply to him
FA.9	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to be able to download all material in a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
VI.15	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to register/log in with minimal details		I can be part of the ToyLabs platform
OU.1	Registration		Ordinary User		to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process		I can have a more complete personal profile

VI.8	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the terms of use of the platform and the NDA		I can choose whether I want to carry on the registration procedure or not
OU.9	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to my Organisation to provide the basic information of the entity		an informative profile of my Organisation becomes available to all
MA.13	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to select which partners from the "Open Request" process to invite to the toy creation process step		I can select other collaborators to work with
PO.9	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to be able to search for a Manufacturer in the platform using the partner matching module		to assign him the responsibility to create my product
PO.12	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		accept (double sign) a signed contract from the manufacturer		I have a trusted and formal relationship with him
PO.10	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to be able to accompany the invitation to a manufacturer with an NDA		I can protect the IPRs of my idea
EX.5	Contract Negotiation		Expert		to sign a contract, send to me by a manufacturer		I can ensure that there is a relationship of trust
VI.6	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to see a sort description of each product, including the product owners' details, and likes		I can find out more about a product and the organisation behind it
MA.4	Product Handling		Manufacturer		to be able to see a list of all products I am handling		I can select details on specific ones
MA.8	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to include an NDA to the invitation from the Partner Matching module to a specific toy creation process		I can protect my IPRs in that process
MA.10	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to launch an "Open Request" call for Collaborators		I can attract those interested to collaborate with me
PO.14	Project Monitoring		Product Owner		to view all information on the product, as selected by the manufacturer		I can have a more detailed view on the different actions and decisions
MA.12	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to view responses from partners that responded to the "Open Request" and signed the NDA contract		I can evaluate which ones to accept

FA.5	Fablab Contract Opportunity		FabLab		to positively reply to "Open Request" calls and sign the NDA attached		I can declare my intention to become a collaborator
FA.7	Feedback to Designs		FabLab		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
PO.13	Project Monitoring		Product Owner		to monitor the overall creation process of a product		I can understand to which state it is
PO.15	Project Monitoring		Product Owner		to be able to see a list of all my products		I can select details on specific ones
OU.3	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to edit my personal profile information		I can have a more complete personal profile
EX.1	Expert Contract Opportunity		Expert		to get notified about a direct invite I might get from a manufacturer		I can reply to him
EX.6	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to be able to download all material in a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
OU.13	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		to be able to join an existing organisation, pending the approval of its Owner		I can collaborate with my co-workers of the same organisation
MA.1	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer		to be able to view invitations from project owners for new project's creations		get notified on whether I have been selected as a manufacturer
OU.8	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to be able to specify a new Organisation that I belong to in case this does not exist		I can add my organisation to the platform and become the Owner of it
OU.26	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User		to comment on a product and take part in an ongoing discussion		to make my opinion heard
MA.2	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer		to be able to reply positive and sign a NDA or negative to project creation invitation		I can notify the project owner of my decision
MA.9	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		see all partners that have signed an NDA to a product		I know with who I am sharing information
PO.11	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to send a contract to a manufacturer (who has signed the NDA)		I can formally engage with him
VI.3	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to view all public products of ToyLabs in the main platform		I can understand which products are supported by the platform

FA.3	Contract Negotiation		FabLab		to be in a position to accept/reject a direct invitation by signing the NDA		I can become a collaborator
FA.4	Contract Negotiation		FabLab		to sign a contract, sent to me by a manufacturer		I can ensure that there is a relationship of trust
VI.7	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to contact the ToyLabs platform operators through a form		I can make contact with them
OU.12	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		register my Organisation if not already done during registration		I can add my organisation to the platform and become the Owner of it
OU.23	Communication Actions		Ordinary User		to be able to view messages sent to me and reply		I can continue communication with an Organisation/ other users
OO.1	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to edit the basic information about my Organisation		an informative profile of my Organisation becomes available to all
EX.4	Contract Negotiation		Expert		to be in a position to accept/reject a direct invitation by signing the NDA		I can become a collaborator

User Stories ranked between 19,99 and 15,00

#	EPIC	As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
VI.17	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to request a reset of my password		I can set a new one in case I forgot it
OU.7	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		I want to be able to ask for becoming validated by the ToyLabs platform		I can become a trusted collaborator
OU.10	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to my Organisation to provide the extended capability information of the entity		a detailed profile of my Organisation's capabilities becomes available to all
MA.29	Design handling		Manufacturer		to create a new "Design" version		I can open up the design phase of the process
OU.11	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to be able to join an existing organisation, pending the approval of its Owner		I can collaborate with my co-workers of the same organisation
EX.2	Expert Contract Opportunity		Expert		to browse through "Open Request" call published by manufacturer		I can find new business opportunities
EX.3	Expert Contract Opportunity		Expert		to positively reply to "Open Request" calls and sign the NDA attached		I can declare my intention to become a collaborator
EX.7	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
VI.16	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to use my social network credentials to register/log in		I can be part of the ToyLabs platform
VI.2	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to go through a short tutorial/help page on how the ToyLabs platform operates		I understand the value and operation principles of the platform
EX.9	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to be able to download all material in a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
OU.4	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to make my profile "private"		I am no longer listed in the public users of the platform

OU.5	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to permanently remove my account credentials from the system		I can no longer log-in and not be contacted by other users
VI.12	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the list of registered organisations in the platform		I can find possible collaborating organisations
PO.3	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		engage in discussions with users of the platform based on my product		I can get online, direct feedback
FA.2	Fablab Contract Opportunity		FabLab		to browse through "Open Request" call published by manufacturer		I can find new business opportunities
MA.5	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to able to initiate the partner matching module and search for partners		I can select other collaborators to work with
OO.2	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to edit the extended capability information of my Organisation		a detailed profile of my Organisation's capabilities becomes available to all
EX.8	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a design version		I can establish a private communication channel
EX.11	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a prototype		I can establish a private communication channel
MA.3	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer		to retrieve, sign and send back a contract sent to me by a product owner		I can then start the production process
FA.10	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
OU.24	Communication Actions		Ordinary User		to get notified when I have a direct message received		I know a response to my request was provided
FA.8	Feedback to Designs		FabLab		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a design version		I can establish a private communication channel
MA.30	Design handling		Manufacturer		to be able to turn the visibility of a "Design" version to public, that will showcase only basic design information		it can be displayed publicly in the ToyLabs showcase page
VI.13	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to display a public AR model of a final product with the help of the ToyLabs AR Engine		I can have a virtual representation of the product in a real setting environment

OU.22	Communication Actions		Ordinary User		to be able to send a direct message to the Organisation behind a product		I establish a communication channel with an Organisation
OU.16	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public designs on the website based on their popularity		I can see the ones with the most comments
OU.25	Communication Actions		Ordinary User		to get notified when a product makes an announcement to its followers		I get instant news directly from the product's Organisation
OO.5	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to make my organisation's profile "public" (default option)		it is listed in the public organisations list of the platform
EX.10	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
OU.27	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User		to comment on a public AR model in the ToyLabs platform		I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
OO.7	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to accept or reject invitations of other people wanting to join my Organisation		I can have all my team online to collaborate
OU.21	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to be able to share information about a product on my social media accounts		so that I further disseminate information about a product
OU.18	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public prototypes on the website based on their popularity		I can see the ones with the most comments
MA.24	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to enable the "influencers' mode" of the sentiment analysis module		I can find people with influencing power in a broad web audience on a specific topic
PO.2	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to issue announcements about my product		I can notify people of important news
OU.15	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public designs on the website based on their creation date		I can see the most recent ones
OU.17	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public prototypes on the website based on their creation date		I can see the most recent ones

User Stories ranked lower than 14,99

#	EPIC	As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
VI.4	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to sort products on the website based on their creation date		I can see the most recent ones
MA.32	Design handling		Manufacturer		to view the feedback of my collaborators on a "Design" version		I can fine tune my idea
MA.40	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer		to view the feedback of my collaborators on a "Prototype" version		I can better understand the feedback from the prototype
MA.41	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer		to view feedback captured from the AR model		I can better understand the feedback from the prototype
FA.11	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a prototype		I can establish a private communication channel
PO.5	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to specify crucial information about my product (like cost, technical requirements, material requirements, etc.) about my product		I can have a thorough description of my product's specifications
OO.8	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to delete my organisation		it is no longer part of the ToyLabs platform
OU.14	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		to be able to leave an already joined organisation		I can no longer see the detailed projects of it
MA.42	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer		to set the privacy category level allowed for AR feedback		I can declare what kind of feedback I welcome (anonymised or not)
OO.4	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to make my organisation's profile "private"		it is no longer listed in the public organisations list of the platform
VI.5	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to sort products on the website based on their popularity		
VI.14	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to provide feedback to AR models in case this is allowed		I can provide my comments without being logged in
MA.28	Design handling		Manufacturer		to create a new "Master" Design		I can have multiple versions of the same master design

OO.9	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to invite other team members to join ToyLabs and my Organisation		I can have all my team online to collaborate
OU.28	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User		to vote specific features on a public AR model, on my mobile device		I can instantly provide feedback
MA.15	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer		see all partners that have signed an NDA to a product		I know with who I am sharing information
MA.19	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to be able to initiate the sentiment analysis module		I can understand the sentiment of users on a product or a manufacturer and trends discussed in web2.0 channels
PO.8	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to choose whether I will create the product on my own or will delegate the manufacturing process		I can become a "manufacturer" or I can have global visibility over the selected manufacturer actions
PO.6	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to archive a finished product		it is not displayed on my dashboard
OO.6	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to get notifications about people asking to join/leave/accept or reject Ownership transfer of my Organisation		I can have an idea on who is a member of my organisation
MA.14	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to decline responses from the "Open Request" process		I can filter out responses that are not interesting to me
MA.16	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer		to send a contract to a collaborator already added to a toy creation process step (have signed the NDA)		I can formally engage with him
OM.1	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to leave an Organisation		I no longer see the data
MA.33	Design handling		Manufacturer		to close a "Design" version		I can move on to another phase or publish an updated design
OO.3	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to share information about my Organisation through my social media accounts		so that I further disseminate information about my Organisation
OU.31	Prototype Request		Ordinary User		to be able to request a prototype of a product		I can have a hands-on experience

MA.21	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to select the social media channels to be used by the sentiment or the trend analysis module		I can understand the opinion or the desire of the crowd in the web
MA.25	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer		to see the positive, negative and other online comments on my product or my brand from the sentiment analysis module		I can define a strategy for improvement
MA.34	Prototype handling		Manufacturer		to open a new "Design" version once the previous one is closed		I work with my collaborators on the improved design that resulted from the previous thread
VI.10	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to change the website's language		I can view information in my mother language
MA.17	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer		accept (double sign) a signed contract from a collaborator		I have a trusted and formal relationship with him
PO.4	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to mark a product as released and update its description		users can find more information about it in the public website
OU.29	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User		to upload a screenshot of the public AR model		I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model
MA.7	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to invite a partner to a step of the toy creation process (Design/Prototype/Mass Creation)		I can explore collaboration opportunities
OO.10	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to be able to remove users from my Organisation		I can manage the access of users to my Organisation's information
MA.18	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer		see all partners that have signed a collaboration contract to a product		I know with whom I have an open contract in a product
MA.23	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to select specific words in the sentiment or trends analysis module		these are used for mining the web
MA.37	Prototype handling		Manufacturer		to populate the "prototype" version with material relevant to this phase (files, specification, cost analyses, etc.)		I can share this information with my future collaborators
MA.20	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to be able to initiate the trend analysis module		Understanding of trends in toy sector, using web2.0 channels

MA.26	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer		to see visualised analytics based on the results of the sentiment or the trend analysis module		I can better understand the results of the module
MA.27	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer		to see related concepts about search terms		Related concepts to search terms may can drive to results about trends and feedback from users
OM.4	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to share information about my Organisation through my social media accounts		so that I further disseminate information about my Organisation
FA.13	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to comment on an AR model in the ToyLabs platform		I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
OU.20	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to be able to view my "Followed" products in a separate screen		I can focus on them
OM.2	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to accept the transfer of the ownership of an Organisation to my Name		I can become the Owner of it
OU.19	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to be able to "follow" a product to add it to my Favourites by hitting "like"		I can receive updates about this product in the future
OM.3	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to reject the transfer of the ownership of an Organisation to my Name		I remain as a simple member of it
MA.22	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to select the other web sources (blogs/forums/pages) to be used by the sentiment or trends analysis module		I can understand sentiments, desires and opinions in specific blogs and web pages
MA.31	Design handling		Manufacturer		to populate the "Design" version with material relevant to this phase (files, specification, cost analyses, etc.)		I can share this information with my future collaborators
FA.12	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to be able to play with controls embed in the AR model		I can have a better experience with the conceptual model
EX.12	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to comment on an AR model in the ToyLabs platform		I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
FA.16	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to be able to suggest partners I have collaborated with in the past		I can indicate to manufacturers collaborates I have good experience with

OO.11	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to be able to transfer the ownership to another member of the organisation		I can leave Ownership to another user
MA.6	Partner Matching		Manufacturer		to see a list of collaborators suggested by partners I already work with		I can build a more trusted cycle of collaboration
MA.36	Prototype handling		Manufacturer		to be able to turn the visibility of a "Prototype" version to public, that will showcase only basic design information		it can be displayed publicly in the ToyLabs showcase page
PO.7	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to specify whether a product belongs to an organisation I am part of or not		I can distinguish ownership between individuals and organisations
VI.9	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to change the accessibility settings on the website's content		I can better access information in case I have a disability
FA.14	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to vote specific features on an AR model, on my mobile device		I can instantly provide feedback
EX.13	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to vote specific features on an AR model, on my mobile device		I can instantly provide feedback
MA.38	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer		to attach an AR model to a prototype		I can share it with collaborators
VI.11	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the list of registered users in the platform		I can find possible collaborators
EX.14	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to upload a screenshot of the AR model		I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model
OU.6	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to choose whether I can hide my profile details in case this is allowed		I can protect my online identity during feedback
FA.15	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to upload a screenshot of the AR model		I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model
MA.39	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer		to accompany the AR model with a simple questionnaire for AR user		they can instantly provide comment from the AR devices

